

LEAF-Net: Local End-to-End Cross-Modal Alignment via Feature Warping for UAV Imagery

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Abstract

Low-altitude UAV RGB-MS imagery supports fine-grained vegetation monitoring but is limited by residual cross-modal misregistration. To address this, we introduce LEAF-Net, a geometry-aware tree detection framework that uses shared Red/Green bands to estimate local displacement fields and warp multispectral features into the RGB reference frame before fusion. Alignment is supervised on spectrally comparable Red/Green content, avoiding direct matching between modality-specific deep features. We evaluate LEAF-Net on UAV orthomosaics from reforestation sites in Senegal. On the original test data, LEAF-Net improves AP50 over both RGB-only detection and multimodal fusion without alignment. Synthetic MS-shift experiments further show improved robustness under misregistration. These results suggest that explicit feature-level alignment improves RGB-MS fusion for UAV-based tree detection under cross-modal misregistration.

Keywords: multimodal deep learning, UAV remote sensing, feature alignment, tree detection, reforestation monitoring

1. Introduction

Multimodal UAV imagery enables fine-grained vegetation monitoring by combining high-resolution RGB structural cues with multispectral (MS) physiological information. Resolving small tree crowns requires low-altitude flights, but this acquisition setting amplifies perspective and relief-displacement effects, meaning RGB and MS orthomosaics often remain locally misaligned even after photogrammetric processing (Turner, Lucieer, and Watson 2012; Aasen et al. 2018; James et al. 2017). These residual offsets, illustrated in Figure 1, decouple RGB structure from MS spectral responses and directly limit feature-level fusion.

Existing approaches only partially address this problem. One option is to pre-register RGB and MS

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

Figure 1: Cross-modal misregistration in low-altitude UAV orthomosaics. Red crosses indicate RGB coordinates, blue crosses indicate corresponding feature locations in the MS-derived image, and black arrows show displacement vectors $\Delta\mathbf{p}$. These spatially varying offsets motivate local alignment before multimodal fusion.

imagery before training using photogrammetric, image-registration, or feature-matching methods (Zhang et al. 2021; Sarlin et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2022). However, this preprocessing step is decoupled from the downstream detection objective and may fail to correct dense, local, depth-dependent parallax. Another option is to rely on implicit multimodal fusion, where the network learns RGB-MS interactions from early band concatenation or attention-based feature mixing (Li, Qiao, and Yang 2025; Shen, Wang, and Jin 2022). These methods can exploit complementary spectral information, but they do not explicitly correct spatial misalignment. When RGB and MS features are locally misregistered, the model may rely mostly on the better-aligned modality, reducing the contribution of MS information and contributing to modality collapse (Huang et al. 2022). Global attention may also add avoidable cost for a problem that is mainly local and geometric.

This motivates a task-driven alignment mechanism that is local, dense, and optimized jointly with detection. Dense correspondence methods from optical flow provide a useful template: they estimate displacement fields using cost volumes and differentiable warping (Dosovitskiy et al. 2015; Sun et al. 2018; Teed and Deng 2020). However, our setting differs from standard optical flow because the goal is not to estimate temporal motion between consecutive frames, but to correct residual misregistration between RGB and MS imagery.

To this end, we introduce **LEAF-Net** (**L**ocal **E**nd-to-end **C**ross-Modal **A**lignment via **F**eature warping), a geometry-aware architecture for joint tree detection and cross-modal alignment. LEAF-Net adapts dense-correspondence principles to RGB-MS UAV imagery by using spectrally shared Red/Green bands as geometric anchors. It models residual RGB-MS misregistration as a local displacement field rather than as a global transformation. Shared Red/Green anchor features are used to construct a bounded local correlation cost volume, from which a lightweight flow predictor estimates dense offsets. These offsets warp MS feature maps into the RGB reference frame before

Figure 2: Overview of LEAF-Net. Shared Red/Green bands guide the estimation of a local displacement field, which warps MS features into the RGB reference frame before gated fusion and tree detection.

fusion, while alignment supervision is imposed on the shared Red/Green bands. This allows the network to learn task-relevant cross-modal registration end-to-end through both the alignment and detection objectives. By integrating local feature alignment directly into the detection pipeline, LEAF-Net provides a task-driven alternative to separate pre-registration and purely implicit multi-modal fusion.

2. Methods

As illustrated in Figure 2, LEAF-Net addresses residual RGB-MS misregistration by learning local feature alignment inside the detection network. The RGB stream acts as the geometric reference, while the MS stream provides complementary vegetation-sensitive information through bands such as RedEdge and NIR. Both streams use CNN-based encoders so that feature locations preserve spatial meaning (Bronstein et al. 2021), which is required for grid-based warping.

The alignment module estimates misregistration from the Red and Green bands available in both sensors. These bands are encoded with a shallow shared encoder and compared within a local search window to build a bounded correlation cost volume, inspired by optical-flow methods. A lightweight flow predictor maps this cost volume to a dense displacement field:

$$\Delta \mathbf{p} = r \tanh(\Psi(\mathbf{C})), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the local correlation volume, Ψ is the flow predictor, and r limits the maximum displacement. This bounded formulation focuses the model on residual local misregistration.

The predicted field warps MS features into the RGB reference frame before fusion. Because the detection loss backpropagates through the fused features, the warping operation, and the flow predictor, the model receives a task-driven alignment signal from the tree detection objective. We further add an auxiliary alignment loss on the shared Red/Green bands: the same field is applied

to the MS Red/Green representation, and the warped result is compared with the RGB Red/Green representation using cosine similarity and gradient consistency. Finally, RGB and aligned MS features are fused using gated fusion and the fused representation is passed to the detection head.

3. Experiments

We evaluate LEAF-Net on a real-world UAV RGB-MS dataset collected for low-altitude reforestation monitoring. The dataset contains trees with varying crown sizes and heights, which makes RGB-MS misregistration spatially variable and challenging for multimodal detection.

3.1. Dataset and Data Acquisition

We conducted a field campaign in autumn 2025 at reforestation sites in Senegal (15.764°N, 15.977°W) managed by Lignaverda (Lignaverda 2026).

UAV Data Acquisition We acquired UAV imagery with a DJI Mavic 3M equipped with an RGB camera and a 4-band MS sensor capturing Green, Red, RedEdge, and NIR bands. To obtain high-resolution imagery suitable for small-tree detection, we flew at 25 m above ground level with 80% image overlap. We performed radiometric calibration using a MicaSense Reflectance Panel 2, used ground control points for georeferencing, and generated RGB and MS orthomosaics using Pix4D software.

Field Inventory and Annotations Tree locations were recorded in the field using an Emlid Reach RTK GNSS system in a base-rover configuration. These field observations were then converted into crown-level bounding-box annotations on the UAV orthomosaics, yielding a final detection dataset of 447 annotated tree instances.

Dataset Preparation To reduce spatial leakage between training and evaluation, we first partitioned the orthomosaics into geographically non-overlapping training, validation, and test regions. Within each split, RGB and MS orthomosaics were tiled into image patches for object detection.

3.2. Experimental Setup

We compare three models to isolate the roles of multispectral information and explicit alignment: an RGB-only detector, a multimodal fusion model without alignment, and the full LEAF-Net model with local feature warping.

All models are first evaluated on the original RGB-MS orthomosaic tiles. To further assess robustness to additional cross-modal misregistration, we apply synthetic global translations to the MS input at test time. For each shift magnitude, each MS tile is translated by the specified number of pixels in a randomly sampled direction, while the RGB tile and ground-truth boxes remain unchanged. These perturbations simulate increasing RGB-MS misalignment beyond the residual offsets already present in the original orthomosaics. We do not use synthetic shift augmentation during training, so this experiment tests whether the learned alignment module generalizes to unseen geometric perturbations. We report AP50 on the held-out test set for the original data and for

each synthetic shift magnitude.

4. Results

Table 1 reports AP50 for the RGB-only detector, multimodal fusion without alignment, and LEAF-Net with local feature warping. On the original RGB-MS orthomosaic tiles, corresponding to 0 px additional MS shift, the RGB-only model obtains 0.5234 AP50. Adding MS information without alignment slightly improves performance to 0.5284, while LEAF-Net reaches 0.5451. This suggests that MS information provides a modest benefit without alignment, while explicit local alignment yields a larger improvement.

Under moderate synthetic MS shifts, LEAF-Net remains more robust than the no-alignment variant. At 8 px and 16 px shifts, local feature warping improves AP50 by +2.51 and +3.38 percentage points, respectively. Since no synthetic shift augmentation was used during training, this suggests that the alignment module provides robustness to moderate residual RGB-MS misregistration.

For larger shifts, both multimodal variants fall below the RGB-only baseline. This indicates that severely misaligned MS information can become harmful once the displacement exceeds the bounded alignment range of LEAF-Net. This behavior is consistent with the model design, which targets residual orthomosaic misregistration rather than arbitrary large cross-modal displacement.

MS shift	RGB only	Fusion w/o align	LEAF-Net w/ align
0 px	0.5234	0.5284	0.5451
8 px	0.5234	0.5330	0.5581
16 px	0.5234	0.5128	0.5466
32 px	0.5234	0.4937	0.4910

Table 1: Robustness to multispectral misalignment. AP50 is reported for an RGB-only detector, multimodal fusion without alignment, and LEAF-Net with local feature warping. Synthetic shifts are applied only to the MS input at test time; therefore, the RGB-only baseline is unaffected by shift magnitude. The 0 px setting corresponds to the original RGB-MS orthomosaic tiles without additional synthetic shift. No synthetic shift augmentation was used during training.

5. Conclusion

We presented LEAF-Net, a geometry-aware framework for RGB-MS UAV tree detection. LEAF-Net uses shared Red/Green bands to estimate local displacement fields and warp MS features into the RGB reference frame before fusion. Results on UAV orthomosaics from Senegal show that this explicit feature-level alignment improves AP50 on the original data and increases robustness to moderate synthetic MS shifts. These findings suggest that local cross-modal alignment is a useful inductive bias for UAV-based object detection when residual RGB-MS misregistration remains after photogrammetric processing.

Acknowledgements This work was supported by the *Chair for AI-based remote sensing for monitoring reforestation success in semi-arid regions* at KU Leuven, funded by Steven Buyse. We thank Lignaverda for their support during data collection and fieldwork.

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